

05 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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24 December 2020

The paper is the fifth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>.

The post is about the scalar property of the units of the structure of discrete space.

Scalars

In geometry a scalar is a sphere. Because every property of the sphere is determined by only one value, its radius. Observable reality is 100% geometrical and the consequence is that at the lowest level of reality a scalar is a sphere.

There exists a scalar field that pervades – during the whole evolution – the whole volume of our universe, the Higgs field.^[1] The Higgs field is not the only universal field, the electric field is a universal field too. There are more fields that are supposed to exist everywhere in the universe, like the magnetic field and the field of gravitation.

However, because the Higgs field is a scalar field, all the scalars of the Higgs field have the same magnitude. There are local exceptions like rest mass carrying particles and of course black holes. Within the boundary of rest mass carrying particles and black holes the magnitude of the scalars of the Higgs field are decreased, creating a supply of energy from the decreased scalar(s) to the electric field around (the so called *Higgs mechanism*).^[2]

A field is a volume that shows variations of a property within the volume of the field. That means that the concept of a field is created with the help of the phenomenological point of view. A clear confirmation of the phenomenological origin of field theory is the brief description at Wikipedia about [field theory \(physics\)](#).

The concept of discrete Euclidean space isn't about the phenomenological point of view, it is about the underlying reality that creates observable reality. The consequence is that the reliability of the research is founded on the geometrical relations. This in contrast with theoretical physics where models are developed to be in line with the experiments. Even if the conceptual framework of the model is violating logic (like the imaginary *asymptotic freedom*).

If I want to know the “physical” properties of the scalar I simply can calculate the geometrical relations inside the scalar. The diagram in figure 1 shows the result.

I can divide the scalar – a sphere – in concentric shells and each shell has the same thickness. For example if the radius of the sphere is 36 cm, every concentric shell is 1 cm. The “push” of the outer shell ($r = 36$) on the adjacent shell ($r = 35$) is equal to the mutual relation between the distinct surface areas. In figure 1 the vertical scale is not equal to the horizontal scale but it is done to show that the resistance of a scalar against deformation is *infinite*. In other words, because the Higgs field is the universal scalar field, the resistance against topological deformation of every unit in discrete space is infinite.

figure 1

The shape of every unit of discrete space is created by an internal spherical shape forming mechanism (see post 4). If I fill a volume completely with units that have identical basic properties and one of these properties is the scalar mechanism, I get the configuration of scalars within the volume that is drawn in figure 2.^{[3][4]}

Every scalar that is part of the flat Higgs field – vacuum space – has 12 adjacent scalars form the units around. Thus every scalar in vacuum space has 12 points of contact.

figure 2

The mutual distance between all the scalars in vacuum space – the points of contact – is $2r$. I can construct a plane in every point of contact at right angles to the line between the centres of 2 adjacent scalars. The result is the image in figure 3. The scalar is a bit transparent to show all the outlines of the 12 planes, a rhombic dodecahedron.

The division of the volume of a unit into an undistorted part of the scalar mechanism – the inscribed sphere – and the remaining deformed part is reason to question the exchange of some volume between these two parts. Because local scalars of the Higgs field can decrease their magnitude under influence of a concentration of energy, the Higgs mechanism.^[2] The creation of rest mass.

If the volume that is exchanged between the 2 parts has no structure, there is no conceptual problem. But if the volume has an internal structure – a stream of small grains – I have to answer the question about the existence of the minimal length scale. Because the units of discrete space exist because these units have a boundary. And if these units are build up by small grains that have a boundary too, why do the units at the size of the minimal length scale exist and not only the small grains?

If I relate the volume of the scalar of a unit in vacuum space with the deformed part of the volume in figure 3 it shows that the mutual relation is determined by 2 irrational

figure 3

numbers, π and the square root of 2 (π and $\sqrt{2}$). It means that the volume of the unit cannot be build up by “grains of volume”.

But this is not the only conclusion. If the scalar and the deformed volume are related by irrational numbers it is impossible that both parts can obtain some kind of a fixed balance between both volumes. In other words, it is impossible that a unit of discrete space can be put in a state of geometrical equilibrium. Because if the latter is possible the concept of discrete space must be wrong (violating the existence of the dynamical nature of our universe).

References:

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Scalar vectors

An internal spherical shape forming mechanism inside a volume means that the volume will “try” to get the shape of a sphere. Figure 1 shows that expanding the inscribed sphere inside a volume – enlarging the radius of the scalar – will decrease the internal force to prevent a deformation of the shape by one or more influences from outside the volume.

But all the units of discrete space share the same basic properties therefore no scalar within vacuum space – see figure 2 – will have a scalar with a dissimilar magnitude like all the other scalars around. In other words, if all the units of discrete space have symmetrical shapes, every scalar will have 12 internal vectors, corresponding with the 12 points of contact with the 12 units around.

figure 4

The image above (4) shows the top view of 4 scalars, one scalar on top of the other 3 scalars. If all the inscribed spheres in vacuum space have exactly the same radius all the vectors within vacuum space have the same magnitude.

I can imagine a solitary unit that isn't part of the structure of discrete space. The shape of the unit must be a sphere because there is no influence from other units around. But I don't know if the volume of the solitary unit is still identical to a real unit of discrete space. Therefore it is difficult to quantify the strength of the resistance against deforming of a scalar in vacuum space.

Figure 5 shows an attempt in which the radius (r_{is}) of the inscribed sphere is set to the value 1 and it corresponds with a spherical mechanism (S_m) of 1. Now a solitary unit with the same invariant volume has a radius of about 1,105 and a spherical mechanism of about 0,818.

figure 5

The size of the volume of the inscribed sphere of a unit in vacuum space ($r_{is} = 1$) is about 74% of the volume of the whole unit.^[4] That means that nearly everywhere in space the remaining $\approx 24\%$ of the volume of the unit is responsible for the topological changes in discrete space. But the diagram in figure 5 don't show any relation between the

resistance against deforming of the $\approx 24\%$ of the volume in comparison with the spherical shape forming mechanism of the scalar.

